

COVID-19 vs ASEAN Energy Sector: Oil & Gas (Q2)

Q2 2020 update on the impact of COVID-19 to the region's oil & gas sector and its recovery way after the difficult period

Rika Safrina and Silvira Ayu Rosalia

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To update the readers on how the COVID-19 pandemic hits the energy sector, and how the recovery road will affect the energy sector in ASEAN, ASEAN Centre for Energy (ACE) releases several energy insights highlighting the impact of COVID-19 in the ASEAN Energy Sector from our archived news. In this insight, we highlight the impact of COVID-19 in the ASEAN Oil and Gas sector.

The global oil market was striving against the plunging oil demand and crashed oil price due to the spread of coronavirus which stroke many aspects during that time. As oil and gas are accountable as the largest energy supply and energy consumption in ASEAN, respectively 60% and 55% in 2017 (ASEAN Energy Database System), and several member states rely their revenue on oil and gas, the impact of COVID-19 pandemic on this sector in ASEAN is inevitable.

Policy-makers and businesses are trying to take adequate measures to overcome the hard time during the pandemic that hit the oil and gas industry. The recent virus curb helped the situation to be rebounded, which provides optimism outlook as stimulant to rearrange the oil and gas strategy in the future.

Turbulent times in oil and gas history

The year 2020 began optimistically, with several new projects commencing across ASEAN, such as the onshore exploration in Myanmar, the LNG-fired power plant in Vietnam, and the opening of oil and gas projects in Indonesia. The significant oil and gas investments were still considered attractive by Thailand and several investors in Indonesia. Malaysia, in the other hand, even aimed for a foreign opportunity. But not long after, the coronavirus concerns started to linger at the end of February.

As depicted in the wordcloud* generated from our archived news about Oil and Gas from January to July 2020 (Figure 1a), popular words such as **demand**, **prices**, and **power** coined in the news. Meanwhile, the word **covid** was not too visible, because only about 25% of the news was related to COVID-19. However, when categorising each word into a negative or positive tone using sentiment analysis**, the words **outbreak** and **virus** became obvious, among other text such as **decline**, **fall**, and **cheap** (Figure 1b).

Figure 1 The word cloud in (a-left) general, and (b-right) sentiment

The imposed movement restrictions for containing the virus spread contributed to the drop of fuel price and demand. It also affected and slowed down several oil projects, including an offshore oil field production and a power plant construction in Cambodia. Another delay of oil refinery and exploration happened in the Philippines as the country continues to grapple with the pandemic bites. Furthermore, the current crisis might act as a catalyst for the energy transition, thus, creating more threat ahead to the oil and gas industry.

Figure 2 Sentiment words per date on news from January to June 2020

Figure 3 West Texas Intermediate oil price on January-June 2020 (data source: [markets insider](#))

Our previous [Q1 energy insight](#) has reported this bleak period in the oil and gas industry, with the plummeted demand and price. However, some countries took advantage of the lower oil price, and the optimism continued to grow with recovery measurement.

This shifted trend and situation around oil and gas sector can be seen in Figure 2 where we plotted the sentiment score per date throughout the first half of 2020. The graph is somewhat in line with the curve of the West Texas Intermediate (WTI) oil price (Figure 3), which reached a minus point on 20 April for the first time in history.

“The winding road as an impact of pandemic gives pressure in the oil and gas market. It became a serious challenge to survive amid unfavourable circumstances, such as putting off some projects, cutting output, and tightening financial policy. The current crisis might also act as an energy transition catalyst, thus the oil and gas sector must be able to adapt to provide clean energy. Regardless, there is still optimism when the easing of containment measures occurred in many countries which bring some relief in the recovery time”
